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RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: Guibi

FIRST NAME: Ashley

PROGRAM CODE: DDIA

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: One

INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma

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Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)
 The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:
 The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)
 The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)
 My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%
 The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

7 key concepts

1. Turabian guidebook (Euclid, period 1)
2. US and UK English (Euclid, period 1)
3. Final Product (Euclid, period 1)
4. End Goal (Euclid, period 1)
5. Response Paper (Euclid, Period 1)
6. Ph.D. dissertation (Euclid, period 1)
7. Dr. Kabiru Gulma (Euclid, period 1)

Commented [GK1]: All the 5-7 key concepts to be listed here and discussed in the paper must come from the period one study materials only

Commented [GK2]: This should be an appropriate citation. For example, (EUCLID 2021, 10) - mind the capitalisation and page numbering. Also, Turabian is not the study material for this period. **Kindly limit yourself to period one course pack for this response paper!**

Commented [GK3]: Review all citations in the paper to conform to the format exemplified above!

THE COMPONENTS OF WRITING AN ESSAY

INTRODUCTION

Period one (1) of the course guides us as students of international academic doctorates on the expected and desired writing style expected by the institution. Period one (1) showcases two different styles of writing, which are the **US and UK English**. These styles differentiate from the spelling to the punctuation. In addition to the style of writing, period one (1) shines the light on the different objectives that the student will be gaining and working with as they move forward into the course. Moving forward into period 1, the reader is presented with the course material and the required texts. Finally, we are introduced to the course instructor and given a background of both his professional and academic achievements.

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1) TURABIAN STYLE

The **Turabian guidebook** for writers offers exceptional, in-depth instruction to those writing research papers. Everything relating to formatting is discussed, from "Parts

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of the Paper" through "Sample Layouts" (including the finer points of copyrights and dedications). With the aid of tables, graphics, and chapters on bibliographies, parenthetical references, note-taking, and citations, the mechanics of style (from abbreviations to quotations) are covered. These include advice on preparing a manuscript, tips on using word processing software, and formatting for the most intricate parts of research papers. It offers rapid, easy-to-understand solutions to your format, intellectual propriety, and academic style concerns. The reference text for the preferred style is this textbook (Turabian), although this course also covers (as instructed by the instructor) additional style guidelines that might be relevant, like the WHO and the Blue Book. Not least, among other things, the course exposes the doctorate student to the "**final product**," in this example, a critique of doctoral theses published by renowned universities in related fields of interest. Along with a textbook that focuses solely on doctorate dissertations, this review is included.

2) COURSE OBJECTIVES/ LEARNING OUTCOMES

This section of period 1 dictates the **end goal** of the course for the student in terms of learning. This includes mandated word templates for word styles (heading 1, heading 2, standard, quote). Utilizing the heading 1, 2, regular, and quote Word styles. At the same time, creating a table of contents automatically. Period accentuates the importance of knowing how to use proper US spelling and punctuation vs. learning to use appropriate British spelling and punctuation. Students will be guided on the rule of citation per Euclid standards to avoid plagiarism. Understanding how to build a Euclid quiz is something that is spoken about in this section. Most importantly, how to write a **response paper** EUCLID standard and, finally, how to assess a Ph.D. dissertation and write graduate- and post-graduate-level research papers.

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3) COURSE INSTRUCTOR

Period one (1) introduces me to the course instructor **Dr. Kabiru Gulma**. He is a Euclid University graduate and the center's go-to person for information on academic writing and publishing. Dr. Gulma also participates in the Internal Quality Assurance (IQA) team and is an auditor for the Ph.D. dissertation panel. Dr. Gulma has a track record of accomplishments in academic publication and writing. He has written three books, several book chapters, more than a dozen peer-reviewed publications, and more than fifty articles. Dr. Gulma reviews publications that go through peer review. Dr. Gulma's job is to give me, as a student, the best faculty support possible while working independently throughout the period. This includes, but is not limited to, assisting students in mastering: The use of Grammarly, great academic/professional paper writing, etc.

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4) CONCLUSION

Period [one \(1\)](#) offered me a general idea of what to anticipate as the course progressed. I'll be expected as a student to be proficient in writing in both US and UK styles. As a researcher penning a research paper, I should be prepared to go deeper into the Turabian method. Students are urged to use the institution's rules, such as the Zotero instructions and the student orientation guidelines. Dr. Gulma will be a pillar of support for me throughout my path because of his extensive academic research and writing expertise. He is the best person to turn to when assistance is needed due to his accumulated academic and professional knowledge over the years.

REFERENCES

[Cleenerwerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui: Euclid University.](#)

Deleted: ¹ "ACA-401D: International Academic Writing (Doctorate) – EUCLID University LMS," accessed June 6, 2023, <https://eucliduniversity.net/courses/aca-401d/>.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.